

PREDICTION OF FIRE DAMAGE TO COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The response of advanced composite structures to fire was investigated. An analytical technique originally developed for ablative materials was adapted to this problem. The technique includes calculation of heat transfer, chemical degradation, production and flow of decomposition gasses and resulting internal pressures, stresses, and failure. Sample analyses illustrated the behavior of composite structures exposed to fire. Simple experiments qualitatively confirmed the analytic results, and provided additional insights. Advantages of composite structures included very long burn-through times, and self insulation of thick structures through blistering. Disadvantages included vulnerability of thin structures and creation of difficult to detect impact-like damage from even brief exposure to fire.

Keywords: composite materials, analytical methods, numerical models, fire, high temperatures, damage, aircraft structures, safety

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Composite materials are increasingly used in critical aerospace structures. For these materials to be used in primary structure of commercial passenger aircraft, their safety and reliability under a variety of circumstances must be assured. This paper addresses the effects of fire on these materials. In-flight cargo or equipment fires could immediately threaten the integrity of an aircraft. Aircraft could be damaged on the ground by fire in ways that might threaten later performance. Perhaps most importantly, after a crash the fuselage of a commercial airliner must remain intact and structurally sound for as long as possible in the presence of major fires to allow crew and passengers to escape. The FAA has initiated a program to greatly reduce fire as a cause of crash fatalities;¹ composite materials may play a major role in achieving this goal.

The response of composite materials to fire or other high heat loading is very different from that of metals. Anisotropic conductivities, usually much lower than those of metals, result in unique thermal responses and temperature distributions. The constituents of composites burn, char or melt at different temperatures and at different rates, resulting in complex degradation and failure behavior. There is an extensive literature on the fire resistance of composite materials used as internal components such as moldings and baggage racks. This literature is primarily concerned with flammability and toxicity of outgassed products, however, and is of little use for assessing structural response. More relevant is work dealing with the response of composite structures to laser and nuclear threats,²⁻⁴ and some limited work on response to fire.^{5,6} These works combine thermal and structural analyses to calculate the response of the structure, but handle chemical degradation and failure mechanisms in approximate or incomplete ways. Recently, a revival of interest in the analysis of ablative composite structures such as rocket nozzles has led to the

publication of a number of works which treat the problem more completely.⁷⁻¹³ These works include consideration of changes in material properties, chemical degradation, production and flow of decomposition gasses, stresses due to all of these factors, damage, and post-damage behavior.

This paper presents an attempt to apply this new analytical capability to the problem of fire damage to aircraft structures. The analysis technique is briefly reviewed, along with the existing material property data base for heat affected composite materials. Sample cases are analyzed, and trends discussed. An ongoing program of simple tests is described, and preliminary results are presented. Finally, conclusions, including important insights into the promise of greater fire resistance through the use of composites, as well as a few potential problems, are discussed.

2. ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUE

The technique used to analyze fire damage to composite structures is a direct adaptation of the thermomechanical behavior analysis method developed by McManus and Springer. It will only be outlined here; it is developed fully in References 8-10.

We consider a fiber-reinforced composite plate of thickness H , width W and length L (Figure 1). The width and length of the plate are large compared to the thickness ($L/H \gg 1$ and $W/H \gg 1$). The plate consists of plies which do not necessarily lie in the plane of the plate, but may be at an angle Φ with respect to the plate surface, although aircraft structures will in general have $\Phi = 0$. Currently, all the plies are assumed to be identical, and have the same uniform thicknesses and material properties.

The plies may be reinforced either by continuous unidirectional fibers, (all fibers being parallel and aligned at an angle Θ , as shown in Figure 1) or by woven fabric. The fibers are assumed to be inert and do not undergo chemical reactions. The exception is at the heated surface where the composite (fiber and matrix) may ablate. The fibers are surrounded by an organic polymer matrix. At high temperatures, the matrix may give off vapors due to the evaporation of absorbed water or other liquids; it also may undergo pyrolysis reactions, which generate volatiles and leave behind a porous skeleton of carbon char.

One side of the plate is insulated and is impermeable to heat and mass flux. The other side is open to the ambient environment, where the heat flux (or the surface temperature) and the normal (pressure) and tangential (shear) loads are specified. The heating and loading may vary with time but are taken to be uniform over the surface. This condition, together with the geometric requirement that the length and width are large compared to the thickness, implies that conditions in the plate vary only through the thickness.

The surface heat flux raises the temperature of the composite, resulting in degradation and charring of the composite. Both the charring of the composite and desorption of moisture absorbed in the composite release gasses which may be trapped or forced to escape through microscopic channels in the composite. In either case, the gas can cause local pressure buildups (Figure 2). This pressure, in combination with thermal and charring stresses and stresses due to externally applied loads, may cause damage in the composite.

A model was developed which predicts the following parameters as functions of time and position inside the composite: temperature, amount of char formed, amount of gas released, gas flow, pressure, stresses and strains, and damage and failure. Although the model was developed with carbon-phenolic and carbon-carbon composites in mind, it captures the phenomena applicable to other types of composites. Only by fully modeling these complex phenomena can the response of composite structures to fire be confidently predicted.

The CHAR computer code was written to solve the equations of the model and to generate numerical results. The CHAR code is written in FORTRAN 77 and can be run on Macintosh, PC, or workstation computers. The input parameters required by the code and the output provided are specified in Reference 10. A user-friendly version of the code with a manual is available from the author.

Figure 1. Geometry of problem.

Figure 2. Internal pressure buildup.

A complete set of required input data was not available for the materials typically used in aircraft structures. Many properties for AS/3501-6 graphite-epoxy composite as functions of temperature were contained in Reference 3. In this reference, endothermic decomposition reactions were crudely modeled as a region of high effective specific heat and jumps in many material properties. This model was recast by assuming an endothermic chemical reaction irreversibly converts the matrix of the material to a char.² Separate virgin material and char properties were defined for input in the CHAR code. Data on gas permeability of the material (a measure of the ease with which internally generated gasses can escape, critical to successful damage calculations in carbon-phenolic composites¹³) was not available. Permeability data collected for carbon-phenolic composites¹⁰ was used in the analyses. To bound the error resulting from this substitution, the effects of changes in permeability values were studied parametrically. Surprisingly, the response of the graphite epoxy structures studied was found to be relatively insensitive to changes in the permeability.

3. SAMPLE ANALYSES

Two cases were studied analytically, corresponding to a small onboard fire and a large fire typical of a crash. In each case, a thin composite laminate ($h = 0.7$ mm, typical of a secondary structure and/or a honeycomb sandwich face sheet), a thick laminate ($h = 10$ mm, typical of primary structure), an intermediate thickness laminate ($h = 2.6$ mm), and aluminum plates of the same thicknesses were analyzed. The fire was modeled as a convective and radiative boundary condition. The flux q delivered to the structure at this boundary was

$$q = h_c(T_\infty - T) - \sigma\epsilon(T^4 - T_r^4) \quad (1)$$

where h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient, T_∞ the flame temperature, T the surface temperature, σ the Stefan-Boltzman constant, ϵ the surface emissivity, and T_r the effective radiative boundary temperature, taken in all cases to be 298 K (25°C). The small fire was modeled as $T_\infty = 773$ K (500°C) and $h_c = 20$ W/m²K, while the large fire was modeled as $T_\infty = 1643$ K (1370°C) and $h_c = 45$ W/m²K. No mechanical load was applied, ambient pressure was assumed to be 1 atm (0.1 MPa) and the initial temperature of the laminates was set at a uniform 25°C. The laminates were assumed to initially contain 1.9% by weight absorbed moisture.

The calculated temperature distributions within the laminates at 10, 20, 30, and 40 seconds after application of fire are shown in Figures 3-7. It was found that damage in the form of delaminations (blisters) was caused by the build-up of internal pressure, primarily due to the vaporization of absorbed moisture. Delaminations formed when the internal pressure exceeded the interlaminar tensile strength of the material. Charring of the matrix took place as well, but only after blistering. The extent of blistering is shown in Figures 3-7 by hatching on the temperature profiles. The thinnest laminate is not shown for the large fire case, as it was entirely blistered within 7.5 seconds.

Two distinct response modes can be seen. Thicker laminates, intensely heated, function as insulators. The surface material reaches high temperatures and blisters. The blisters actually aid the insulating effect, as the blistered material is less thermally conducting than the undamaged material. Material to the rear of the laminate remains relatively cool and mechanically sound. Thinner laminates rise in temperature more evenly, and the entire laminate reaches blistering and/or charring temperatures at about the same time. Catastrophic failure could be expected at that point if the laminate was carrying any mechanical load. The definition of "thick" and "thin" varies with heating rate. The intermediate thickness laminate behaves as a thick laminate in the large fire, blistering on the surface and self-insulating (Figure 4), but behaves as a thin laminate in the smaller one, rising in temperature throughout the laminate (Figure 6).

In contrast, all of the aluminum panels rise almost uniformly in temperature. The performance of a composite laminate and an equivalent thickness aluminum panel are compared in Figure 8. Thin composite panels blister at a temperature between the softening and melting temperature of aluminum. Hence under some loading conditions, the thin composite panels may mechanically fail before equivalent aluminum ones. The thick panels, especially in the large fire case, are always ultimately more resistant than equivalent aluminum panels, due to their self-insulating capability. In no case do the composite structures burn through. Even when the matrix chars, the graphite fibers continue to exist. The thin aluminum panels quickly melt. A disadvantage of composites can be seen at short exposure times however; the surface of the composite very quickly reaches high temperatures, implying some damage to the structure.

Figure 3. Thick panel, large fire.

Figure 4. Medium thickness panel, large fire.

Figure 5. Thick panel, small fire.

Figure 6. Medium thickness panel, small fire.

Figure 7. Thin panel, small fire.

Figure 8. Aluminum vs. composite.

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A series of simple experiments has been initiated to correlate the above analyses. Flat laminates and honeycomb-core panels will be exposed, unloaded, to fire typical of the large fire case studied above. Damage will be assessed visually by examining the surface as well as by microscopic inspection of a cut cross-section after fire exposure. These observations will be used to correlate charring and blistering predictions. Thermocouples will provide temperature data for correlations, and both the tensile and compressive residual strength of the specimens will be measured at room temperature after fire exposure. At the time of this writing, some honeycomb panels have been tested. These tests will be described below.

The specimens tested consisted of sandwich panels with two composite face sheets around a Nomex honeycomb core. The specimens measured 35 cm by 5 cm. At each end, 7.5 cm of the core was replaced by high-density aluminum honeycomb core, and fiberglass loading tabs were attached to both face sheets, to facilitate gripping during tensile testing.

The face sheets were constructed of AW370-5H/3501-6S graphite-epoxy cloth plies cut to size and laid up according to standard Technology Laboratory for Advanced Composites (TELAC) procedures.¹⁴ The face sheets were autoclave cured, and then bonded to the 2.5 cm thick cores using film adhesive. A third bonding was used to attach the loading tabs. The face sheet layups, face sheet thicknesses, and number of samples constructed are shown on Table 1. The specimen geometry is illustrated in Figure 9.

The specimens were heated at a constant rate for varying amounts of time. The heat source was a Bunsen burner using methane. The specimens were placed in machined fire-brick holders such that an area 5 cm long and 5 cm wide, on only one side of the specimen, was exposed to the flame. The heating rate was calibrated using an instrumented aluminum block, the thermal properties of which were known, placed in the specimen holder in place of the specimen. It was found that the burner consistently delivered a flux consistent with a convective heat transfer coefficient of 45 W/m²K and a flame temperature of 1370°C. Ten and forty second burn times were used. To assess burn-through performance, a single spare specimen was burned for approximately 5 minutes.

After burning, one sample of each type was sectioned for examination. The others were tested using an MTS tensile testing machine. The specimens were gripped using hydraulic grips, and tested at a constant cross-head speed. Load was monitored using a load cell, and the test continued until all load-carrying capability was lost. Control (unburned) specimens were also tested. Some specimens were instrumented with longitudinal strain gages attached to both the burned and unburned face sheets on the mid-line of the specimens, halfway between the burned area and the loading tabs.

Figure 9. Test specimen geometry.

Table 1. Number of specimens of each type for each test and burn time.

Face Sheet		Tensile Tests			Observations	
Layup	Thickness (mm)	unheated	10 sec.	40 sec.	10 sec.	40 sec.
[0,45] ₁	0.7	1	3	3	1	1
[0,45] ₅	1.3	1	3	3	1	1
[0,45] ₂₅	2.6	1	3	3	1	1

5. RESULTS

It was found that only the thinnest facesheets showed visible damage after 10 second burns. Evidence of matrix degradation such as discoloration was seen, but no blistering or delamination. After 40 seconds, the thin face sheets were entirely delaminated and charred, the mid-thickness specimens showed some delamination damage, and the thickest specimens showed some damage but no delamination. In no case, even the five minute burn-through test, was erosion of the graphite fibers noted. Comparison of the test observations with the analytical predictions shows the latter to be conservative. More delamination damage was predicted by the analysis than was observed in the tests. Qualitatively, the analytical results were confirmed in that thin laminates showed damage throughout, while thicker laminates were damaged only at the surface.

The residual strength test results are summarized in Figure 10. The residual strength of the panels, normalized by the unburned strength as determined from the control specimens, is plotted against exposure time for each face-sheet type. Not surprisingly, the thicker facesheets retain more strength than the thin ones. The panel strength is not reduced much below 50% of the original value due to the fact that only one face sheet is exposed to the fire. The other face sheet remained undamaged in all cases. It can also be seen that for even small heating times, significant strength is lost. Figure 11 shows the correlation between the strength deterioration of the panel and the observed damage. As expected, these results indicate a deterioration in tensile strength with increased visible damage. They also indicate that even with no apparent visible damage, 15-20% of the panel's tensile strength can be lost.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The method utilized, despite current limitations such as lack of good material data, reveals significant characteristics of the response of composite structures to fires. An ongoing test program is in qualitative agreement with the analytical results, and has yielded additional insight into the residual strength of fire-damaged laminates.

Figure 10. Normalized residual strength.

Figure 11. Residual strength correlated with visible damage.

Composites have excellent resistance to burn-through, due to the stability of the graphite fibers. Therefore, the fire safety issue for these structures is the damage done by the fire in the form of delamination, blistering, charring or invisible heat damage, and the resulting loss of mechanical strength. Two distinct damage modes were noted. Thin structure tends to rise in temperature relatively uniformly, and is damaged throughout the thickness. Thick structure self-insulates, reaching high temperatures and blistering near the surface but remaining relatively cool and mechanically sound in the interior. This behavior was qualitatively verified by tests. The tests revealed a disturbing phenomena, however. Laminates with minor fire damage, not visible to simple inspection, showed moderate loss of residual strength. This problem is similar to that of impact, in that apparently minor, difficult to detect damage has a large effect on the integrity of the structure.

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COMPOSITE FIRE-RESISTANT PANELS

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INTRODUCTION

Composite materials used for their resistance to flame and to very high temperatures already have a number of fields of application (the aeronautics industry, for example).

The Sandwich material, presented jointly by EDF and HAMON Industrie Thermique makes it possible to obtain a CF/PF degree of 1 hour 30 minutes, while maintaining excellent mechanical characteristics, despite its light weight.

1. PRESENTATION AND USE OF THE PRODUCT

The Sandwich material is composed of two laminated phenolic glass-resin facings and a core of phenolic resin based synthactic foam.

The structures and thicknesses are defined according to the mechanical stresses and CF degree to be obtained.

The manufacturing principle enables panels to be made to shape so as to meet with the requirements of architects and design departments.

The facings are made by contact moulding using a mould of the shape of the finished product. Preparing the mould does not involve any special operations as compared with traditional moulding techniques.

Certain polyester gel coats developed by manufacturers can be used as a top coat. Precautions must, however, be taken and specific fire resistance tests are indispensable.

The type and number of the various glass reinforcements (fibre, mats), whose binders are compatible with phenolic resins are laid out in accordance with the permissible mechanical stresses involved, both at ambient temperature and during fire.